

DAEMON

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Deliverable 6.1

Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (CoDEP) for Y1

Abstract

This deliverable presents the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan (CoDEP) of the H2020 DAEMON project. Here we provide the list of activities under each part of the plan as well as the targeted metrics. In addition, we introduce an initial standardization roadmap, including the identification of relevant standard development organizations and relevant open-source projects. Finally, early achievements in some of the activities are also listed.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	7
2	Communication plan.....	9
3	Dissemination plan.....	11
3.1	Dissemination work plan for year 1	12
3.2	Synergies with other projects.....	14
4	Exploitation plan	16
4.1	Products and services.....	16
4.1.1	Vendors and service providers.....	16
4.1.2	Network operator	17
4.1.3	Small and medium enterprises	18
4.1.4	Academia and research centers	19
4.1.5	Exploitation plan of products and platforms for vendors and SMEs.....	20
4.2	Patents and licensing.....	22
4.3	Standardization plan.....	23
4.3.1	Standardization work plan for year 1	23
4.3.2	Relevant standardization activities.....	23
4.3.3	DAEMON standardization timeline	28
4.4	Open-Source plan.....	30
4.4.1	Open-Source work plan for year 1	30
4.4.2	Relevant Open-Source activities	31
4.4.3	DAEMON open-source time line	31
5	Early achievements	32
5.1	Communication activities	32
5.1.1	News and press releases.....	32
5.1.2	Web, social media, and project communication material	32
5.1.3	Communication talks and other actions.....	36
5.2	Dissemination activities	36
5.2.1	Publications and technical dissemination.....	36
5.2.2	Synergies with other projects.....	37
5.3	Exploitation activities.....	37
5.3.1	Standardization	38
5.3.2	Open-Source activities	38
5.3.3	Bachelor, Master, PhD Theses/Courses and Internships.....	38
6	References	39

List of Figures

Figure 1. DAEMON Communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan.....	7
Figure 2. Resources repository with Open Access DOIs dissemination workflow.....	12
Figure 3. Timeline of SDOs relevant to DAEMON.....	29
Figure 4. Open-source time plan.....	31
Figure 5. DAEMON website's landing page.....	32
Figure 6. Most visited page.....	33
Figure 7. Most used web explorers & devices used to access the website.....	33
Figure 8. Geographical distribution of the website accesses.....	33
Figure 9. DAEMON's Twitter analytics.....	34
Figure 10. DAEMON's Twitter account profile.....	34
Figure 11. DAEMON's LinkedIn account analytics.....	35
Figure 12. DAEMON's Facebook account analytics.....	35
Figure 13. DAEMON's Instagram account profile.....	35
Figure 14. The H2020 European Project DAEMON Tri-Fold Kick-off Brochure.....	36

List of Tables

Table 1. H2020 DAEMON communication plan.....	10
Table 2. H2020 DAEMON dissemination plan.....	12
Table 3. Synergies with other projects.....	14
Table 4. Exploitation plan for vendors and service providers.....	17
Table 5. Exploitation plan for network operators.....	17
Table 6. Exploitation plan for small and medium enterprises.....	18
Table 7. Exploitation for academia and research centers.....	19
Table 8. Exploitation for vendors and SMEs.....	20
Table 9. Mapping of DAEMON innovations to SDOs.....	28
Table 10. Communication talks.....	36
Table 11. Publications in scientific conferences and workshops.....	36
Table 12. Publications in scientific journals.....	37
Table 13. DAEMON-related bachelor, master and PhD theses, and internships.....	38

List of Acronyms

3GPP	– Third Generation Partnership Project
5GPPP	– 5G Public Private Partnership
AI	– Artificial Intelligence
B5G	– Beyond 5G
CoDEP	– Communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan
DOI	– Digital Object Identifier System
ETSI	– European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FOSS	– Free and open-source software
IEEE	– Institute of Electronics and Electrical Engineering
IETF	– Internet Engineering Task Force
IPR	– Intellectual Property Rights
IRTF	– Internet Research Task Force
ITU-T	– International Telecommunications Union – Telecommunications standardization sector
KPI	– Key Performance Indicator
MANO	– Management and orchestration
ML	– Machine Learning
NFV	– Network Function Virtualization
NI	– Network Intelligence
O-RAN	– Operator Defined Next Generation RANG
PoC	– Proof of Concept
R&D	– Research and Development
RAN	– Radio Access Network
RIS	– Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
SDO	– Standard Development Organization
SM	– Standardization manager
SME	– Small and medium-sized enterprise
TSG	– Technical Specification Groups
VNF	– Virtual Network Function
WG	– Working Group

Executive summary

The main contributions of this document are:

- Presentation of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan (CoDEP)
- Presentation of the early achievements according to this plan.

DAEMON's CoDEP includes communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. **Communication** includes all the activities related to the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's own community. This includes explaining its research in layman's terms to the media and the public. **Dissemination** includes activities related to raising awareness of its results in a technical community working on the same research field. In general, this will be done through publications, and participation and organization of technical events. Finally, **exploitation** (in accordance with the European IPR Helpdesk) covers activities aiming at using the results in further research activities other than those covered by the project, such as developing, creating and marketing products or processes, creating and providing a service, or standardization activities. Particular emphasis is given to standardization in this deliverable; the initial roadmap defined is also presented.

The **Raise Awareness phase**, during the initial stages of the project, focuses on communication activities (e.g., setting up the web portal and social media accounts and high-level project presentations) to make the project known not just to the technical community but to a larger audience outside the project topics, including the public. Dissemination and standardization activities also start in this phase with preliminary technical ideas. In the **Presentation of Results phase**, dissemination and exploitation activities increase their intensity, since the architecture and NI design efforts will have produced meaningful results. Initial demonstrations of specific concepts of the architecture and NI solutions are also expected during this phase. However, it is in the **Demos and PoCs phase** where demonstration activities involving multiple blocks of the architecture working in an integrated way are expected. Finally, the **Long-lasting Impact phase** refers to other research or exploitation actions taken once the project is finished. This includes shaping the topics and framework of future research projects, exploiting DAEMON NI concepts in a market-oriented way by incorporating them into products and services, and leaving a footprint in standards through project contributions. The plan defines the various undertaken activities, and defines related target metrics. In accordance with the plan, some early results have already been produced. Some highlights follow:

- Communication
 - Design of promotion material, website, and creation of news, social media accounts, along with initial actions to raise awareness about the project through these means. This already resulted in over 1000 visits to the website and an increasing impact through social media.
 - Communication talks, a brochure and other events to present the scope of the project.
- Dissemination
 - Nine accepted conference publications, some of them jointly with other projects and in top venues (e.g., IEEE INFOCOM, AAAI, etc.).
 - Four accepted publications in top-tier (Q1) journals (e.g., IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, etc.).
 - Participation in various working groups to join efforts with other 5GPPP projects.
- Exploitation, including standardization
 - Creation of the standardization management role.
 - Identification of relevant SDOs for networking (e.g., 3GPP, IETF, ETSI, O-RAN) and monitoring of groups of interest for potential contributions.
 - Identification of relevant open-source projects (e.g., srsRAN [3], Eclipse Zenoh [5], Eclipse fog05 [6]).
 - Definition of the initial standardization roadmap according to the timelines of the SDOs and the project.

1 Introduction

DAEMON's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (CoDEP) covers the following three types of activities [1][2]:

- **Communication activities:** These activities encompass all actions concerning the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's own community. In this way, the target of this activity is the general public, i.e., non-specialists, and the message shall be encoded in a way that is understood by this audience.
- **Dissemination activities:** These activities have the goal of raising awareness of DAEMON's results in a technical community, i.e., working in the same field of research. These activities will usually be performed through peer-reviewed publications in scientific conferences and journals, and through participation and organization of technical events (e.g., workshops, tutorials, etc.).
- **Exploitation activities:** These activities cover initiatives that foster further research activities, i.e., other than those covered by DAEMON. These include (i) activities to develop, create and market products or processes, (ii) activities to create and provide a service, and (iii) standardization activities.

Figure 1. DAEMON Communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan.

Figure 1 presents the different project milestones and deliverables that concern the implementation of the CoDEP, as well as the different activities and phases during the project execution. All these activities will be executed in parallel; however, special emphasis will be given to the appropriate one depending on each phase of the project.

In detail, during the "Raise Awareness" phase, at the beginning of the project, the focus is on communication activities such as setting up the website, social media coverage, and high-level overview presentations. The goal hence, at this early stage of the project, is to make the project known, not only within the research community, but also to a larger audience including the general public. As depicted in **Figure 1**, dissemination and standardization activities also start at this phase of the project, with preliminary technical contributions. Specifically, this early stage focuses on the following set of activities:

- Website and social media accounts.
- Project brochure.
- Press releases.
- High-level project presentation and participation at events to explain project scope.
- Participation in events for a general audience (e.g., open science week).
- Lectures at university courses.

The aforementioned activities are allocated more effort at the beginning of the project, in order to raise awareness and set up the initial framework used for communication throughout the project, but they continue on during the whole timespan of DAEMON.

During the "Presentation of results" phase, DAEMON will increase focus on dissemination and exploitation activities. Analytical results and results gathered via simulations are expected during this stage (e.g., in

top-tier scientific conferences and workshops), but also preliminary demonstrations (e.g., at events such as Mobile World Congress or EUCNC). In more detail, the focus will be put into the following set of activities:

- Dissemination
 - Publication of research results in scientific conferences, workshops and journals.
 - Enrolment of PhD and Master students on the topics of the project.
 - Participation in public exhibitions and demonstrations.
 - Organization of special events (e.g., technical workshops).
 - Collaboration with other projects.
- Exploitation
 - Identification of products and services, integrating NI spawning from DAEMON work.
 - Issuing patents and licensing.
 - Contribution to relevant open-source software projects.
 - Contribution to standardization bodies.

During the “Demos and PoCs” phase, DAEMON will re-focus its efforts into the development of demonstration and proof-of-concept (PoC) prototypes of designed NI-aided systems. These activities will help to validate the NI mechanisms derived in other work packages but also, in the context of WP6, will help disseminating and communicating the results of the project to both the scientific community and the general public at large.

The final stage of the CoDEP is named “Long-lasting impact”, which will begin towards the end of the project implementation and will last several months after DAEMON has finished. During this stage, partners of DAEMON will keep disseminating results of the project and exploiting network intelligence designed and developed during DAEMON, by impacting on the product or service portfolio of the vendors in the consortium, or through enforcing IPR and licenses.

This CoDEP will be periodically updated throughout the lifetime of the project. This will allow us to accommodate new activities such as new collaboration or dissemination opportunities should they appear. In the rest of this document, we present in detail the plan of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities for the first year of the project. In addition, we will complement our plan with early achievements obtained within the first three months of the project.

2 Communication plan

H2020 DAEMON will create, from the early stages of the project, a basic set of necessary presentation materials targeted for various audience types:

A **communication package** that will be used as the core communication measure to promote the project. The communication package considers the official website that will serve as a central hub for obtaining detailed information about the action. The project website includes pointers to all the documentation, code and data repositories generated by the action. Presentation material will also be part of the communication package, including flyers, leaflets, and posters to be used in all occasions for communication, and displaying an easily recognized official DAEMON logo specifically designed for the project. Assets of sufficient quality will be made publicly available under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license, and uploaded to the Zenodo repository with their respective open access DOIs in order to facilitate linking and citations. Allowing others to use our assets with attribution will increase the project's exposure and impact. Media assets will be made available for downloading from the project's website, and through other appropriate channels (e.g., Zenodo, YouTube, Vimeo, or SlideShare). The project partners will then carry out a number of communication activities tailored to each specific audience, as detailed next. Table 1 summarizes the different activities in the DAEMON communication plan and provides metrics to assess their success.

Communication to the general public. DAEMON establishes a presence on popular social media largely used by the non-expert public, such as Twitter, Instagram, Facebook and LinkedIn, where regular updates on the action progress are posted. Social media is fully integrated with the project website, and will be used to advertise the project results, announce events such as conferences and showcases, inform about the most recent results and reports, and provide a platform for discussion. In addition, the official social media accounts of all partners are linked (e.g., via following, re-posting, or re-tweeting) to the DAEMON accounts, so as to maximize its reach and visibility. Streaming platforms like YouTube will be leveraged to publish videos showcasing trials and panels in order to provide a simple and effective way of accessing the project results and main ideas. Webcasts will also be employed as an effective way to share slightly more technical information about the knowledge and tools produced by DAEMON, for instance with hands-on sessions explaining the fundamentals of the project solutions. Finally, the partners will produce white papers aimed at explaining the evolutions of network technologies to the public. Efforts will also be made to reach out to traditional media such as newspapers, TV, or radio, as this is a very effective way to make the general public aware of the benefits to society resulting from research projects. When addressing these media, emphasis will be placed on the benefits of the project for society. Indeed, use cases such as the ones related to culture or education may raise the interest of the general public, which may help to reach this kind of audience. It is worth noting that several project partners have dedicated communications offices, excellent track records of public engagement activities, and well-established links with the media; they have already succeeded in having impact on mass media (e.g., the New York Times, the Irish Times, Forbes, Spectrum, De Standaard, De Morgen, Flanders Today, The Financial Times, The Guardian, The Times, O Globo, Il Corriere della Sera or El Pais), as well as on national broadcasters like RTE (Ireland) and VRT (Belgium), to name just a few. In addition, internal magazines published by project partners and aimed at the general public, such as the IMEC magazinell, will be used to communicate the project results.

Communication to students and prospective researchers. The approaches to NI integration in future-generation mobile networks developed by DAEMON will be included in teaching material presented to students of courses on B5G technologies, including classes of the Master programs in Telematics Engineering, Telecommunications Engineering and Big Data Analytics at UC3M, classes of the Data Science and Technology Master at TU Delft, and Master of Computer Science, Educational Master of Science and Technology, and Master of Informatics at University of Antwerp. Industrial partners will present the DAEMON activities during seminars they regularly hold as integral part of university courses, such as that on "5G Service Automation" offered by the University of Antwerp. Internships for graduate students and industrial PhD programmes will be offered by the industrial partners on the research topics of DAEMON, exposing such students to problems and solutions investigated by the project, and starting their training in developing the necessary skills to address the challenges of B5G systems. Furthermore, NBL plans to conduct an industrial PhD working on DAEMON. In addition, partners will take full advantage of open research events and science fairs to showcase the project results to the public, and in particular to students. This will include participation in initiatives such as those in the context of European Researchers' Night¹ or broadcasted talks.

The following table includes the targeted audience, the related activities, the timing, and the metrics of the communication activities, including quantified goals. DAEMON aims to register and publish open-access communication related assets and advertise them in the main social networks.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/research/mariecurieactions/actions/get-funding/european-researchers-night-2021_en.

Table 1. H2020 DAEMON communication plan.

Audience	Activity	Timing	Metric
All, General public, Research	Project website. DAEMON will share its concepts, results and achievements through its dedicated project website. The website is synchronized with the project social network accounts, and will be the primary tool of communication and promotion of the project.	M1 and cont. update	All sort of Google Analytics including country of access, number of unique visits per page, total number of visits, and retention index.
All, General public	Press releases, posters, leaflets. DAEMON will prepare and distribute project poster, press releases and leaflets to raise public awareness.	M3 and event-driven	1 leaflet and 1 poster available at Month 3. Published press releases (target: two per year) Assets with open access DOIs published in Zenodo with certain metrics as number of online reads and downloads.
General public	Public Communication. DAEMON project, including its impact on the transformation of vertical industry, will regularly be promoted through participation and organization of events for society at large and distribution through social media. We will also make use of EC communication tools and magazines.	M1 and event-driven	Num. of events organized / attended (target: at least one org. per year) Assets with open access DOIs published in Zenodo with certain metrics as number of online reads and downloads.
All, General public, Research	Social Networks. DAEMON is present on the main social network with official profiles and project pages. DAEMON social network profiles will advertise all outputs from all other work packages. Additionally, these profiles will constantly inform by means of short feeds the main results and events that the DAEMON consortium will deliver.	M1 and cont. update	Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram analytics, including number of likes, re-publishing, and number and types of comments.
General public, Interest groups	Video. DAEMON will work on the creation of public videos to advertise the proposed network scenarios and their capabilities.	Event-driven	Videos of all demo activities available in the web, its Youtube channel, and Zenodo (open access DOIs). Number of likes and views.
Students	Lecture materials related with DAEMON will be introduced in academic courses and webinars taught by partners	Potentially every 6 months	Number of related courses where project topics are introduced

3 Dissemination plan

The purpose of the dissemination plan is to guarantee that all concepts and technologies developed in the DAEMON project are disseminated adequately to relevant entities, including standards development organizations. Dissemination and Collaboration (primarily within the 5G-PPP) activities are expected to be conducted in Year 1 to help promote the project concept and initial results to the large European and more International R&D community and raise opportunities for synergy with other projects and activities. The plan will pursue the following goals: (i) creating a radical shift in the mindset of the networking research and development community that span both industry and academia towards a pragmatic, holistic integration of AI into future network architectures and equipment; (ii) foster the widespread adoption of the AI-based architecture and solutions developed by DAEMON beyond the manufacturers and operators of the consortium; (iii) protect the project findings to secure the commercial advantage of DAEMON partners while fostering the adoption of the technology beyond the consortium.

This section presents the plan in Year 1, and reports the achievements for dissemination and collaboration activities. The dissemination activities are carried out continuously when there is the appropriate combination of availability of project results and opportunity. In this respect, project milestones are a key source of dissemination. As far as dissemination is concerned, the following activities are expected:

Publications in selected journals and magazines, such as IEEE/ACM journals, transactions and magazines (e.g., IEEE TMC, ACM/IEEE TON, IEEE JSAC, IEEE TNSM, IEEE Communications Magazine, IEEE Network) and reputed international conferences (e.g., IEEE INFOCOM, IEEE ICC, IEEE GLOBECOM, ACM MobiCom, ACM CoNEXT, AAAI, ICML, IEEE SECON, IFIP/IEEE IM, IFIP Networking, IEEE/IFIP NOMS, IEEE CNMS).

Collaborations with EU and other research projects through 5G-PPP working groups, network2020, and other H2020 projects in support of the 5G-PPP commitments and towards the realization of the B5G vision.

Presentations and participation on behalf of the project in research-oriented workshops, industry-oriented workshops (e.g., ETSI workshops on standardization), technology platforms and any other similar forum, including participation on academic and industrial panels organized in these events.

Participation in public **exhibitions and demonstrations** for academia (e.g., demonstrations in conferences) and industry (e.g., Mobile World Congress, EUCNC, IWPC, Edge Computing World, Bell Labs Future X days, Eclipse IoT and Native Edge day, SDN and NFV World Congress or equivalent) to disseminate research work to create awareness of DAEMON technology and applications.

Organization of events, such as tutorials and/or workshops, collocated with well-established conferences (e.g., CONNECT, EUCNC, IEEE ICC, IEEE Globecom) to showcase DAEMON results.

In general terms, DAEMON will openly publish several resources, whether they are more related to research and industry (e.g., papers, data-sets), or to public communications (e.g., slides, general documents). They will all have an open-access DOI, optimizing citations and/or re-usability of our results and supporting the freedom of sharing DAEMON results while avoiding limits to knowledge distribution. The resources will be hosted in Zenodo, the general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. Hence, the main Daemon project and resources indexer is OpenAIRE – an H2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 777541. **Figure 2** summarizes the workflow, where the main points to highlight are:

- All DAEMON results are provided as resources, which are uploaded in Zenodo. We request an open-access DOI if the resource does not have one, otherwise the original open-access DOI is re-used.
- In case of copyrighted documents, pre-prints are uploaded requesting an open-access DOI. The new DOI is linked in Zenodo with the copyrighted DOI to compute the total metrics/analytics jointly.
- Related resources are referenced by their different DOIs (e.g., a conference paper with the data-set generated in the experiments, and the slides of its presentation in the venue)
- We have created a Zenodo community to reflect the DAEMON consortium, where we are managing all open-access resources. It is accessible at <https://zenodo.org/communities/h2020daemon/>.
- The H2020 DAEMON project itself is indexed in OpenAIRE by the grant agreement No. 101017109. The displayed information is based on the CORDA repository and Zenodo resources. It is accessible at https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::4184e4627d0cae4849077e9275689c2f.
- H2020 DAEMON resources define as a funding acknowledgment the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation grant No. 101017109. That is how OpenAIRE auto-index resources uploaded to Zenodo with the DAEMON OpenAIRE page mentioned in the point above.
- Last, but not least, analytics such as number of reads and downloads, are calculated by Zenodo and automatically populated to OpenAIRE.

Figure 2. Resources repository with Open Access DOIs dissemination workflow.

3.1 Dissemination work plan for year 1

The dissemination activities will be steered towards generating impact through peer-reviewed publications, presentations, talks, demonstrations, panels, workshops, and events. The goals set in Year 1 include:

- Submission of at least 20 scientific articles for publication at reputed conferences and journals by Year 1.
- Submission of at least 30 contributions to SDOs, such as 3GPP, IETF, ETSI, IEEE, ITU over the lifetime of the project.
- Submission of at least 2 joint documents scientific / articles / publications for publication at reputed conferences and journals together with EU and international research projects, e.g., through 5G-PPP working groups, or working groups of other platforms, such as network2020).
- Demonstration of project related prototypes or solutions at least 1 flagship event (e.g., MWC / EUCNC) on Year 1.
- Organization of at least 1 research- or industry-oriented workshop on year 1.
- Participation in at least 1 research- or industry-oriented workshop on year 1.
- Participation in at least 1 open-source project over the lifetime of the project.
- Filing at least 20 patent applications over the lifetime of the project.
- Addition of core skills for technology development within the project into academic curriculums, along with the proposal of PhD and MSc theses on specific topics on DAEMON research agenda.

The following table summarizes the dissemination plan.

Table 2. H2020 DAEMON dissemination plan.

Audience	Activity	Timing	Metric
Academic and industrial research	DAEMON aims at publishing its work in selected, high impact-factor journals and magazines on communications/networking (e.g., IEEE Communication Magazine, IEEE JSAC), and reputed international conferences (e.g., ICC, Mobicom, Globecom, CoNEXT, EUCNC). An appropriate balance between academic and industrial awareness will be sought.	Continuous	At least 20 publications per year in top-tier scientific journals and conferences.
Other research projects	Collaboration with other EU and international research projects (e.g., through 5G-PPP working groups, or	5G-PPP WGs & ad hoc bi-lateral collaboration	Num. of meetings attended (target: at least two per year).

	working groups of other platforms, such as network2020) will also be key towards a coordinated action inside the 5G-PPP and with other H2020 projects related with the design of B5G technologies		Num. of joint documents generated (target: at least two per year).
Mostly academia, but also industry	Organization, presentations and participation in the organization of events (e.g., panels, targeted workshops, workshops co-located with relevant conferences, special sessions) and participation as keynote speaker, panelist, etc., thanks to important vendors, technology providers and operators, high-tech SMEs, and reputed academic organizations within the consortium.	Participation in one event per year One workshop organized	Organization of one 30-people workshop co-located with a major conference (e.g., EUCNC, IEEE WCNC, ICC, INFOCOM) with 70% satisfaction in the workshop quality poll for attendees. Participation in workshops: we measure the number of events (target: at least one per year), we will measure the metrics (web access, cites) of work presented to assess its impact.
Industry	Exploitation workshop. Chaired by the innovation manager and specifically devoted to maximizing the exploitation outcomes of the project in terms of standardization, patenting/licensing, and products and services. Experts on innovation from the various companies representing all industrial sectors already in the project (verticals, operators, vendors, and SMEs and external experts acting as advisors on maximizing the exploitation outcome of the project.	Two workshop org. before M28	One 30-people exploitation workshop before the end of the project with 70% satisfaction in the poll for attendees.
Mostly industry, but also academia	Technology demonstration. The project team believes that the realization of proofs-of-concept is the key to maximize innovation potential. DAEMON will participate in demonstrations of key project components in exhibition booths in fairs, such as those of EUCNC, or industrial events, such as Mobile World Congress (MWC), where some of partners have regularly exhibited.	Approx. every 6 months	Technology demonstration in at least two events per year. Three demonstration deliverables are planned during the project. More demonstrations in several events are targeted.
Industry	Though being part of exploitation activities, the participation in standardization efforts of DAEMON also offers an indirect way to disseminate the results of the project to the industrial community. Nevertheless, there are other non-traditional ways of standardizing (e.g., OPNFV, OpenStack) , such as contributing, and publishing open-source software (part of DAEMON exploitation plan), which may become a de facto standard.	Continuous meetings Participation in at least one open-source project.	Participation in at least one open-source project.

3.2 Synergies with other projects

In this section we have identified a set of ongoing projects (by the time the project starts), which have results that may impact DAEMON. For all these projects, there is a DAEMON partner involved, hence we can use this already established relation to maintain a cooperation between projects. Only a selection of projects is listed below.

Table 3. Synergies with other projects.

Project name	Short description	Technical relationship	DAEMON contact
Ongoing EU H2020 projects			
RISE6G	NEC is Technical Manager in both DAEMON and RISE6G. The focus of RISE6G plans of reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) matches perfectly Task 3.3.	Innovations on intelligent reconfigurable surfaces	NEC
5Growth	5Growth has designed a management and orchestration platform for vertical services using (shared) 5G infrastructure. 5Growth's innovations on AI/ML-as-a-service and next-generation RANs are highly related to many tasks in DAEMON's WP2 and WP3.	Smart orchestration and control, AI/ML platform, next-generation RANs	NEC, UC3M, NBL, TID
5G-TOURS	UC3M is beneficiary partner for both DAEMON and 5G-TOURS. As 5G-TOURS is setting up innovative use-cases related to the adoption of 5G, DAEMON will seek collaboration for the possible deployment of NI into these large-scale testbed	AI Orchestration, Machine Learning	UC3M, WINGS
HEXA-X	Hexa-X is the flagship project for the research on 6G communications. Through the partners that work on both projects, DAEMON will foster the collaboration in some of the most innovative topics such as deep learning and reconfigurable intelligent surfaces.	Deep Learning, RIS	UC3M, WINGS, TID, NBL
5G-CARMEN	The objective of 5G-CARMEN is to leverage on the most recent 5G advances to provide a multi-tenant platform that can support the automotive sector delivering safer, greener, and more intelligent transportation with the ultimate goal of enabling self-driving cars. DEAMON will seek collaboration toward the possibility of bring some of the architectural designs of the multi-tenant infrastructure and use them to deploy and test AI-based resource management at the edge in the Smart	AI Orchestration and resource management at the edge	IMEC, NEC, WINGS

	Highway tested located in the Belgium zone.		
National and internal projects			
Smart Highway project	Belgian national project on connected and automated vehicles. The infrastructure resulting from the Smart Highway project will be enhanced by DAEMON's edge computing resource allocation and services	AI-based multitenant resource allocation at the edge	IMEC
Content and Context based Adaptation in Mobile Networks	French national project aiming at evaluating analytics for classification, prediction and anomaly detection using real-world high-detail mobile network data, for applications to cognitive networks	Data-driven AI design for network management	IMDEA
Methods and Tools for the Deployment of Eco-efficient Applications in the Edge	Spanish national project aiming to propose techniques and tools to reduce the energy consumption and latency of application on Edge Computing systems	Smart energy consumption and latency of deployments in the Edge	UMA
Languages and Ecosystems for the Variability Analysis, Derivation, Resolution and Materialization Focused in the Architecture and Quality Attributes	Spanish national project that will provide an advanced variability modelling tools for several contexts, aiming to automatically generate optimal and eco-efficient solutions	Advanced model-driven analysis to orchestrate network quality attributes	UMA
Efficient Deployment of Augmented Reality in the Edge	Spanish national project on a framework for the optimal deployment of augmented reality applications in the Edge	Smart deployment of advanced applications in the Edge	UMA

Furthermore, project partners participate to multiple 5GPPP working groups, namely:

- Pre-Standardization
- Vision and Societal Challenges
- 5G Architecture
- Software Networks
- 5G Automotive
- Test, Measurements and KPI Validation.

Their scope is described at: <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-work-groups/>. This participation includes presenting and representing the project in all periodic meetings that are organized and participation in joint actions (e.g., co-organization of events, joint documents/papers, joint demonstrations).

Additionally, the project also participates in the 5GPPP boards towards a tight coordination with the rest of 5GPPP projects: the project coordinator in the steering board and the technical manager in the technology board.

4 Exploitation plan

The DAEMON vision is to set forth a pragmatic approach to NI design. The project will carry out a systematic analysis of which NI tasks are appropriately solved with AI models, providing a solid set of guidelines for the use of machine learning in network functions. For those problems where AI is a suitable tool, DAEMON will design tailored AI models that respond to the specific needs of network functions, taking advantage of the most recent advances in machine learning. Building on these models, DAEMON will design an end-to-end NI-native architecture for B5G that fully coordinates NI-assisted functionalities.

DAEMON's exploitation plan puts forward processes and structures for monitoring innovation throughout the lifetime of the project. The objectives of the exploitation plan include:

- Identification and dynamic management of the exploitation management approach.
- Continuously monitor market, technology and policy trends related to NI.
- Liaise with stakeholders to acquire their feedback on the usability of the services to be offered.
- Continuously monitor all major project activities related to the deliverables with high innovation potential.
- Continuously sync with Work Package leaders to assess the innovation level of the activities executed therein against the Exploitation plan.
- Assess the level of innovation at project level, utilizing **Innovation Metrics**, a set of performance indicators, which are related to the **Key Innovation Areas** of DAEMON.

Most importantly, we aim to achieve a good understanding and continuous (throughout the whole lifetime of the project) monitoring of the NI landscape/domain, in terms of market needs, developments and opportunities. Within this landscape, we aim to assess how DAEMON results align and integrate, while responding to real needs from stakeholders.

DAEMON defined a series of performance metrics (the Innovation Metrics) that we will use throughout the lifetime of the project to capture its status in term of exploitation of the work.

KPI	Target	Relevant Initiatives for Target
Submitted contributions to standards	30	3GPP, ETSI, O-RAN, ITU, ONF, IETF
Patent applications	20	Contributions in the main innovation areas DAEMON targets.
Open-source contributions	6	srsRAN (formerly srsLTE), Eclipse, ONF
Participation in industry events	10	MWC, IWPC, etc.
Demonstrators	4	Radio, Orchestration, Management, Edge
Organized industrial workshops	2	Over 30 attendees each

4.1 Products and services

The main areas of DAEMON innovation aim to address map to the NI-assisted functionalities addressed by DAEMON, which are as follows:

- F1: RIS Control
- F2: Multi-timescale Edge resource management
- F3: In-backhaul support for service intelligence
- F4 Compute-aware radio scheduling
- F5 Energy-aware VNF placement
- F6 Self-learning MANO
- F7 Capacity forecasting
- F8 Automated anomaly response.

4.1.1 Vendors and service providers

Vendors participating in DAEMON are set to lead the future market of B5G technologies by developing novel hardware, software platforms and services. Three time-frames were defined:

1. Short term - Opportunity to get their R&D efforts into focus and evolve their current product portfolio with vertical requirements as input.
2. Medium term - Use findings to understand verticals requirements and needs related to the various industry markets, and to identify gaps in 5G End-to-End connectivity platforms in order to develop innovative, flexible solutions for B5G systems.
3. Long term – Exploitation of results by further feeding their product and business units.

Table 4. *Exploitation plan for vendors and service providers.*

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
NEC	<p>NEC plans to use the results and findings from DAEMON to evolve the current vRAN and O-RAN product portfolio, and to develop an added-value management and orchestration platform that brings the flexibility of SDN/NFV to NEC line of products, impacting the Mobile Radio Access Networks and Mobile Wireless Networking business units.</p> <p>The project results will be used to demonstrate the benefits of the designed orchestration platform both to NEC development groups and potential customers, e.g., European network operators. NEC expects to derive a converged view about gaps and choke-points in today's technology for mobile carrier networks, the collaborative definition of requirements and findings about new concepts for B5G that shall support NEC's strategy and approach in directing its standardization roadmap in global Standards Development Organizations, such as the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) and the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), in different areas to build a solid standards and technology base for the 5G communication system. With the motivation to serve a variety of verticals as well as mobile and stationary device types with different communication characteristics, requirements, duty cycles, traffic patterns, constraints and functional capabilities, NEC believes that the 5G Control- and Data-Plane can optimize the use of network resources on one hand, and ensure the end-to-end service quality experienced through end devices on the other hand, by enabling smart connectivity and associated tailored provisioning, selection and configuration of basic and value-adding services.</p>
NBL	<p>NBL plans to use the project results to evolve the current NOKIA product portfolio on orchestration solutions, towards an automated service life-cycle management that can facilitate an energy-efficient and elastic slicing of the network. Specifically, DAEMON's (NI-based) orchestration and scaling solutions is aimed to be integrated into the several NOKIA product families. NBL will also exploit DAEMON's solution platform via demonstrating internally under the umbrella of NOKIA or externally to the customers in order to explore and expand NOKIA's future product portfolio. The DAEMON project results will be presented to and discussed with the relevant NOKIA business units, as well as with the NOKIA teams actively participating in standardization. NOKIA expects that on the one hand through these interactions the product innovation will be improved and standards (IETF, 3GPP, ETSI, etc.) will be influenced, and, on the other hand, the DAEMON research will solve imminent real-world problems.</p>

4.1.2 Network operator

Network operators will evaluate how to best fulfil the requirements and service portfolio to vertical industry over their network, as well as how to shape their relationship with them. Three time-frames were defined:

1. Short term – Foresee a direct enhancement of their service portfolio by integrating novel forecasting and resiliency workflows into their production systems.
2. Medium term – Operators will gather the know-how for the planning and design of B5G networks.
3. Long term – Operators will apply the experience gained during the development of DAEMON innovations to contribute to the definition of B5G services for their customers.

Table 5. *Exploitation plan for network operators.*

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
TID	<p>TID aims at exploiting DAEMON's results jointly with the business and Telefonica's operation units as follows: (i) improve or develop new methods to operational assessment of network systems, (ii) derive innovative products or services based on DAEMON technology, and (iii) submit patents to protect TID findings. TID will work to create new products that offer better network management, with particular emphasis on pro-active approaches to tackle anomalies. The team involved in DAEMON is currently leading the internal innovation project ARIANA (Artificial Intelligence for Automated Network Actions), which aims to integrate artificial intelligence models within Telefonica's network operations for cognitive maintenance. Through internal innovation processes, TID will implement DAEMON AI-based solutions for anomaly detection in the big data platforms of linked stakeholders, including mobile operators such as O2 UK or Vivo Brazil, as well as global platform operators, such as Telefonica Global Solutions Roaming platform.</p>

OTE	OTE is highly interested in accelerating the development and deployment of modern and innovative telecommunication services and facilities, as those intended to be developed in DAEMON. Thus, OTE intends to exploit the anticipated DAEMON-based findings in terms of delivering pioneering services with strong user engagement by further promoting his competencies in the field of the telecommunication networks market arena at national and at European level. The modern and quite innovative features of the DAEMON findings may be able to influence, to a significant extent, future market-related policies, by offering important advantages for a more effective usage either of existing or of planned -to be developed- facilities. The related DAEMON-based solutions may have dramatic effects on the market sector and this might be a beneficial advantage for the company, especially to offer competitive solutions that could facilitate the market transition towards a real environment.
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4.1.3 Small and medium enterprises

SMEs plan to evolve their products in their specific fields of interest. Three time-frames were defined:

1. Short term – SMEs will exploit from the technology created by DAEMON by contributing to open-source projects and training courses on SDN, NFV, MEC architectures and cloud platforms.
2. Medium/Long term – SMEs could design novel concepts, inspired from DAEMON results to feed-back their product portfolio, which will foresee in the long term an increase in their competitiveness for consultancy services.

Table 6. Exploitation plan for small and medium enterprises.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
ADL	ADLINK seeks to exploit DAEMON innovations related to AI-based management applied to edge and fog infrastructure and data-critical platforms. Specifically, the expected innovations of DAEMON will enable ADLINK to augment its current intelligent computing platform for Edge Computing with a more dynamic management of the resources and services provisioned at the Edge. ADLINK seeks the transfer of the developed technologies by first fostering open-source projects to later build a complete value chain. Part of DAEMON innovations will be fed into the open-source project Eclipse fog05 & Eclipse zenoh currently led by ADLINK. The aim of fog05 is to provide a decentralized infrastructure for provisioning and managing resources across the network to accommodate highly heterogeneous environments that include extremely resource-constrained nodes. The aim of Eclipse zenoh is to provide a protocol suite for adaptive and distributed data-sharing, to enhance data distribution and flexibility
SRS	SRS is an Irish SME providing full-stack SDR solutions for 4G and 5G systems. SRS UE and eNodeB/gNodeB stacks target x86, ARM and FPGA hardware platforms and our open, modular architecture supports highly customized, special-purpose systems. SRS adopts a unique business model that combines open-source and commercial licenses. Thanks to DAEMON, SRS will push forward its UE and gNodeB solutions, expanding and improving them for B5G systems. Specifically, the activities carried out in DAEMON will allow testing and strengthening the SRS 5G product portfolio, supporting the company in the addition of new features and improved performance. On the one hand, this will benefit the overall R&D community, which uses SRS' open-source solutions; on the other hand, it will allow SRS to present new product offerings to its commercial partners, promoting and accelerating the development of SRS' B5G product suite.
WINGS	WINGS is an SME that delivers solutions (software and hardware) for various verticals, namely for the areas: (1) environment (air quality/pollution, sea and land aspects), (2) networks and infrastructures (water/energy/gas, transportation, construction infrastructures); (3) production and manufacturing, which covers industry 4.0, logistics, aquaculture and food safety; (4) service sectors, with an emphasis on health. The solutions rely on: (a) IoT devices with embedded intelligence, (b) advanced wireless connectivity, cloud and big data platforms; (c) AI mechanisms; (d) visualization, which range from mobile applications and dashboards to AR/VR. The WINGS AI mechanisms resources for achieving a high performance and resilient operation. In this respect, through DAEMON, WINGS will enhance its AI competences, especially in the direction of obtaining resilient / robust and trustworthy AI, i.e., mechanisms capable of identifying and negotiating on infrastructure resources, and others capable of managing protecting the vertical AI mechanisms. The developed functionality will be exploited in the WINGS platforms,

	which will have advanced functionality in the vertical domain and in the interaction with the infrastructure.
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4.1.4 Academia and research centers

The Universities and R&D centers participating in DAEMON consortium are interested in building on and further developing existing research strength in the networking research community. Two time-frames were defined:

1. Short/Medium term – academia will improve the knowledge in 5G and B5G, multi-domain orchestration, and slicing, transferring it to the industry.
2. Medium/Long term – the patent and license rewards will help to undertake future European and international research, which will contribute towards further collaborative research possibilities with the project partners and others.

Table 7. *Exploitation for academia and research centers.*

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
IMDEA	IMDEA is committed to support the transfer of technology to the industrial sector, in order to improve its capacity for innovation and competitiveness, as well as to spin-off-companies in order to promote the release of new products and services to the global market. In this context, DAEMON will offer new opportunities to IMDEA researchers to develop novel NI solutions to be transferred into products through the wide network of collaborations that IMDEA has established with the telecommunication industry. In addition, DAEMON will support the deployment of a new programmable network testbed at IMDEA to be integrated in the existing 5TONIC platform, jointly created with Telefonica, which involves the leading European industry players in 5G. Finally, DAEMON will allow IMDEA to recruit and train PhD students and postdoctoral fellows, creating new expertise at the interface of machine learning and mobile networking critical to the European industry.
IMEC	IMEC is a research institute that realizes exploitation of its R&D results to industry via industrial affiliation programs, bilateral projects, IP transfer and licensing, and occasionally through the creation of spin-off companies. The research carried out as part of DAEMON will help IMEC to develop novel solutions of industrial value in wireless communications and AI applied on network management (MEC orchestration, spectrum sharing, and collaborative learning). The knowledge and expertise gained from DAEMON will be very relevant to extend IMEC's 5G test facilities, which are an important asset for both the research community and industrial partners. Moreover, the IMEC IDLab is also embedded within the University of Antwerp, and the knowledge gained from the project will be exploited to support advanced engineering master courses to train future wireless engineers.
UMA	UMA plans to exploit the results of the DAEMON project, applying them to other ongoing research projects like MEDEA: MEthods and tools for the Deployment of energy-efficient Edge computing Applications and LEIA: Efficient Deployment of Augmented Reality Environments on the Edge. The DAEMON project gives us the opportunity to increase our knowledge of 5G technologies so that we can extend our energy efficient software solutions including the particularities of 5G networks. This will allow us to broaden the venues where to publish the research group results with top-rated conference and journals in the networks area. We also plan to continue our high publication rate in forums like SPL conference, and Information and Software Technology, Ad hoc networks or Future Generation of Computer Systems journals. On the other hand, the team at UMA has a strong relationship with many of the software companies located at the Andalusia Technology Part (http://www.pta.es/), and our participation in DAEMON will allow us to increase our visibility in the area of sustainable 5G solutions. We plan to contact some of these companies to invite them to contribute to the validation of the DAEMON project results in industrial environments. UMA will be in position to offer technical advice to companies about software sustainability in 5G/Edge/IoT environments, and offer the open-source results of the DAEMON to the network communication community. Regarding the academic activities at UMA, we expect to enrich existing Master courses about advance telecommunication networks and Telematics Engineering with the results of this project, and to offer tutorials, organize workshops and different teaching activities to disseminate the new expertise acquired under this project to the academic and industrial community in Malaga and Spain.
UC3M	UC3M plans to use the results of the DAEMON project mainly along three lines.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen the academic leadership: the leading role of UC3M in this area has been recognized by the research community, and the participation of UC3M in the DAEMON project allows to publish research results in top-rated conferences and journals, which helps to further strengthen UC3M's position and increase its visibility as one of the top academic institutions active in the field of the application of Artificial Intelligence to networks. In particular, UC3M has already published some of the results in top venues such as ACM MOBICOM, IEEE INFOCOM AND IEEE JSAC, among others. • Foster the technology transfers to enterprises: technology transfer to enterprises is one of the key activities of UC3M. This is being achieved through the standardization and open-source software development, among other activities. DAEMON will reinforce this kind of activities. In particular, UC3M is very active at ETSI ENI and ITU-T standards groups, where it is collaborating with other companies, which are also part of the consortium. • To consolidate the academic courses portfolio: according to several national rankings, UC3M is classified among the top universities in Spain for computer science and telecommunication network studies. The knowledge achieved from the participation in DAEMON provides innovative content to the courses being taught. In particular, UC3M is teaching several master's degrees closely related to DAEMON which are being fed with the knowledge gained from the project: the Big Data MSc, the 5G MSc, the SDN/NFV MSc, the Connected Industry 4.0 MSc, and the MSc in Telematics Engineering.
TUD	<p>TU Delft plans to leverage the results of DAEMON in the following three ways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen the academic leadership: the research activities and the multifaceted collaboration activities with the partners of the project are expected to reinforce the academic profile of TUD in this area. Furthermore, we plan to leverage this opportunity in order to increase our research portfolio with problems that are related to next generation mobile networks and with data-driven evaluation techniques for network orchestration algorithms. First-tier conference and journal venues will be targeted for publication of our results; while we plan to participate in the organization of conference workshops, special issues in journals, and tutorial lectures in relevant venues. • Technology transfer: we will explore potential venues for technology transfer, in collaboration with the industry partners of the consortium, but also with the locally-based enterprises and using the technology transfer program of TU Delft. • Funding Diversification: we will use the results and our experience in DAEMON to apply for additional funding, towards the end of its lifetime, in national funding agencies, and other suitable venues. • Enrich relevant academic courses: the learning outcomes of DAEMON will feed existing courses that are organized in the Software Technology Department of TU Delft, but we will also explore the possibility of developing new courses entirely dedicated to and aligned with the mission of DAEMON (network intelligence algorithms and techniques).

4.1.5 Exploitation plan of products and platforms for vendors and SMEs

In the following table, a detailed description of the platform and products for vendors and SMEs according to the exploitation plan is reported.

Table 8. Exploitation for vendors and SMEs.

Partner	Product/platform	Description of impact on platform/product	DAEMON innovation Area
NEC	NEC O-RAN product portfolio	NEC's RAN Intelligent Controllers for O-RAN Compatible RANs will be highly benefited with the outcome of DAEMON's research. The objective is to derive data collection and decision-making entities both at near-real-time and non-real-time timescales.	RAN orchestration
	NEC 5G orchestration platform	SDN/NFV-based centralized resource management orchestrator for mobile transport domains and network slice orchestration. NEC's orchestration platform comprises a series of tools and automated decision-making entity that merge prediction and machine learning to derive cost-efficient network slicing mechanisms. DAEMON novel orchestration	End-to-end orchestration

		solutions for SLA monitoring and management, and automated network slice management will have a potential impact on the evolution of this product.	
	Net2Vec	Net2Vec is a flexible high-performance platform that allows the execution of deep learning algorithms in the communication network. The monitoring platform of DAEMON and its interfaces with high-speed data processing platforms can have an impact on the evolutions of this product.	All NI
	NEC E-RAN (MEC platform)	NEC's In-Building Small Cell Solutions are easy to install and can be used for WIFI like fast deployment. DAEMON innovations on control loops for service orchestration and programmable traffic management schemes can potentially be integrated in the evolutions of this product. http://www.nec.com/en/global/solutions/nsp/sc2/sol/s02.html	Edge orchestration
NBL	Digital Operations Center	The DO Center provides an agile and modular orchestration for managing service orchestration across virtualized and hybrid networks. It is expected that DAEMON results on, e.g., intelligent placement of VNFs, scaling up/down and in/out, cooperation of controller operating at different timescales, will steer DO innovation.	End-to-end orchestrator
	CloudBand product family	The CloudBand product family, consisting of an NFV resource and network service orchestrator built for OpenStack and VMware, provides two main functions. As a network service orchestrator, the system onboards network services, automates their lifecycles, and provides monitoring and troubleshooting tools. As a resource orchestrator, it administers, monitors and optimizes NFV infrastructure resources across geographically distributed NFV infrastructure nodes. DAEMON innovation pertaining to energy-aware placement and close loop control are expected to impact the (future) list of features of the CloudBand product family.	End-to-end orchestrator
	FlowOne	The research carried out in DAEMON will allow enhancing FlowOne, which provides an agile and modular orchestration for managing service orchestration across virtualized and hybrid networks	Edge orchestrator
WINGS	AIRWINGS	Product platform regarding Air Quality. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Advanced components for having advanced, robust, resilient and trustworthy AI mechanisms: resource request and reallocations, means for improving the AI performance. As all the products have an AI component, it will be important to have mechanisms (at infrastructure and vertical domains) for management, in order to guarantee resilience and also generate trust.	Energy-aware VNF placement (F5), Self-learning MANO (F6), Automated anomaly response (F8)
	ARTEMIS	Product platform regarding Utilities. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above.	Energy-aware VNF placement (F5), Self-learning MANO (F6), Automated anomaly response (F8)
	WINGSPARK	Product platform regarding Transportation and Parking. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above.	Energy-aware VNF placement (F5), Self-learning MANO (F6), Automated anomaly response (F8)

	AQUAWINGS	Product platform regarding Aquaculture. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above.	Energy-aware VNF placement (F5), Self-learning MANO (F6), Automated anomaly response (F8)
	STARLIT	Product platform regarding the Health sector. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above.	Energy-aware VNF placement (F5), Self-learning MANO (F6), Automated anomaly response (F8)
	AGNES	Product platform regarding Food safety. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above.	Energy-aware VNF placement (F5), Self-learning MANO (F6), Automated anomaly response (F8)
ADL	Eclipse fog05	Eclipse fog05 provides a decentralized infrastructure for provisioning and managing resources across the network to accommodate highly heterogeneous environments that include extremely resource-constrained nodes. DAEMON innovative orchestration solutions for SLA monitoring and management will have a potential impact on the evolution of this product.	Edge orchestration
	Eclipse zenoh	Eclipse zenoh provides a protocol suite for adaptive and distributed data-sharing, to enhance data distribution and flexibility. DAEMON monitoring platform and its interfaces with high-speed data processing can have an impact on the evolutions of this product.	Distributed data-management
SRS	srsRAN	srsRAN is a fully open-source 4G and 5G suite including complete UE, RAN and Core network implementations. During 2021, srsRAN will provide one of the first FOSS 5G NSA RANs for public use. With this srsRAN became the new name for srsLTE, as the project begins to focus more on the RAN element of 5G networks. Within the DAEMON project, srsRAN will be leveraged to develop and demonstrate the AI-enabled Network Intelligence envisaged by the project. It is hoped that the advancements made during the DAEMON project will inform the ongoing design and development of srsRAN with features and interfaces to support NI assisted network orchestration and optimization.	RAN Orchestration

4.2 Patents and licensing

DAEMON project addresses an area that provides significant opportunities for standard essential patents. All partners are committed to producing European IPR as important channel for exploiting the project's outcomes. Partners have it a strong background with over 40 patents related to DAEMON's agenda. At least 20 patents are expected to be filed in the context of DAEMON or in topics closely related to DAEMON.

It has to be noted that, after submitting a patent application, it typically takes about one to three years to be granted, sometimes significantly longer. It is also common to file additional divisional/continuing applications several years after the original filing. This means it can take several years before the final protection scope is known, and the time may vary significantly.

Manufacturers can also use patented systems or patented methods in products of their portfolio. In this case, the patent department inside the company typically activates a continuous monitoring of possible infringement typically targeting main competitors operated on the same market segment. Infringement detection and the relevant legal contention can also bring to additional revenues from the invention.

Finally, patents may lead to subsequent licensing, depending on the interests of the partners in exploiting their inventions for their products/solutions or by selling the license to 3rd parties leveraging on licensing revenues. The licensing options are also available for patents filed by academic institutions in the consortium.

4.3 Standardization plan

Maximizing the impact of the project innovations on present and future standardization bodies and industry forums, has been set as a key objective to help create opportunities for commercial exploitation of the project outcome. To this end, DAEMON has appointed Dr. Xi Li, from NEC, as Standardization Manager (SM) to centralize and coordinate all the effort that has the potential of contributing to relevant SDOs.

This section presents first the plan for the activities and achievements that will be undertaken on standardization. These contributions are expected to successfully influence SDOs activities, for example in 3GPP Releases 17, 18 and 19, ETSI MEC, ETSI NFV, ETSI ENI, ITU-T FG ML5G or ITU-T FG NET2030, O-RAN, leveraging the bridging role of industrial partners with leading and active experts in the SDOs.

4.3.1 Standardization work plan for year 1

The project has set the following three objectives for the standardization activities:

- Create and maintain a project standardization activity roadmap. This roadmap will capture the standardization activities that may influence or get influenced by the project technological innovations. It will keep track of existing or upcoming industry specifications or recommendations that may affect the project technological choices and identify opportunities for the project to contribute its proposed solutions to present and future standardization groups.
- Disseminate the project into the standardization forums to raise awareness and help create an opportunity for standardization exploitation.
- Contribute through the partners (individually or jointly) with project-related technology proposals into the relevant standardization forums.

The above objectives remain applicable over the whole project duration. With focus on Year 1, it is anticipated that the activities will first involve the creation of the project standardization activity roadmap. As the design of the project solutions progresses, we anticipate seeing more efforts spent on standardization dissemination and contributions.

4.3.2 Relevant standardization activities

4.3.2.1 3GPP

3GPP covers cellular telecommunications technologies, including radio access network (RAN), core network (CN) and service capabilities, which provide a complete system description for mobile telecommunications. The 3GPP specifications provides hooks for non-radio access to the core network, and for interworking with non-3GPP networks. 3GPP specifications and studies are contribution-driven, by member companies, in Working Groups and at the Technical Specification Group level. The three Technical Specification Groups (TSG) in 3GPP are; Radio Access Networks (RAN), Services & Systems Aspects (SA), Core Network & Terminals (CT).

3GPP is the main SDO in DAEMON project targeting at specifications of radio access networks (RAN) and core networks (CN) of cellular communication systems. The release 17 is anticipated to be completed in Q2 of 2021 and release 18 is expected to follow.

Several study items (SI) and working items (WI) relating to DAEMON have been identified by 3GPP in SA and RAN working groups in release 17, as listed in detail below.

3GPP SA2: SA WG2 is in charge of developing the Stage 2 of the 3GPP network. Based on the service requirements elaborated by SA1, SA2 identifies the main functions and entities of the network, how these entities are linked to each other and the information they exchange. DAEMON will push recommendations based on the design and testing of its proposed NI architecture into relevant work and study items in SA2; those include items linked to network automation, TS23.288“Architecture enhancements for 5G System (5GS) to support network data analytics services”[8], and more in general all procedures related to the Network Data Analytics function.

3GPP RAN1/RAN2/RAN3: RAN WG1, WG2 and WG3 are in charge of the specification of the physical layer of the radio interfaces, its architecture and protocols, including the physical layer definition as well as its connecting link to upper layers. Most relevant to DAEMON are the SIs/WIs related to the New Radio

(NR) Access Technology, where the project will contribute with its innovations on computational-aware radio scheduling and on intelligent surfaces.

3GPP SA5: The 3GPP SA5 defines the management architecture of the 3GPP Networks, specifying elements and interfaces that are used to manage both the network (in all of its domains) and the services provided on top. Multiple DAEMON technologies (i.e., NI architecture, sustainable orchestration, dedicated NI solutions for specific network functionalities) will dictate the requirements for new features on the network management side. As a result, DAEMON will provide 3GPP SA5 with recommendations for the inclusion new data analytics services to be provided to network functions and to the orchestration system as a whole.

The planned contributions from the project should be submitted to 3GPP meetings by 3GPP member organizations. The [meeting calendar](#) describes the schedule of the meetings. 3GPP Release cycle is approximately 15 months. There are plenary sessions that approves the content of the release before the release cycle starts.

4.3.2.2 [IETF & IRTF](#)

The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) is a large open international community of network designers, operators, vendors, and researchers concerned with the evolution of the Internet architecture and the smooth operation of the Internet. The technical work of the IETF is done in Working Groups (WG), which are organized by topic into several Areas. Much of the work is handled via mailing lists. The IETF holds meetings three times per year.

The IETF working groups are grouped into areas, and managed by Area Directors, or ADs. The ADs are members of the Internet Engineering Steering Group ([IESG](#)). Providing architectural oversight is the Internet Architecture Board, ([IAB](#)).

The Internet Research Task Force ([IRTF](#)) focuses on longer term research issues related to the Internet while the parallel organization, [IETF](#), focuses on the shorter term issues of engineering and standards making.

The potential innovations on IETF and IRTF associated with the DAEMON are expected to be related to new orchestration approaches and enhancements to service provisioning are related to the efforts in IETF about service function chaining, network management, reliable wireless, security for IoT.

The main working groups of IETF related to DAEMON are: SFC WG, ANIMA WG, NMRG, and COIN RG. Contributions are made in the form of Internet-Drafts, which are submitted (typically associated to a specific WG) for anybody to read and comment. Drafts matching a given WG milestone can be asked for adoption by a WG, and if so, the document starts becoming a "product of the IETF", and typically ends up being published as an RFC. The submission window only closes for a couple of weeks before each of the 3 physical meetings that take place per year.

There are no releases in IETF. And each document has their own lifetime. WG has their milestones which are typically not scheduled for more than 1.5 years, but in practical terms, most of the documents have cycles spanning for 3-4 years from first submission (as individual document) until publication as RFC.

The following subsections describe several related WGs. Among them, SFC, NMRG and WG COIN topics that may be impacted by the work executed in the DAEMON project.

The **Service Function Chaining (SFC) WG** works on Informational applicability documents that show how the technology, meta-data, and associated control-plane mechanisms can be used in specific use-cases. The SFC WG may work on Informational documents that provide operational considerations.

The **WG ANIMA** specifies Generic use cases of Autonomic Network and new GRASP extensions/options for them, including bulk transfer, DNS-SD interworking, autonomic resource management, autonomic SLA assurance, autonomic multi-tenant management, autonomic network measurement.

The **Network Management Research Group (NMRG)** provides a forum for researchers to explore new technologies for the management of the Internet. In particular, the NMRG will work on solutions for problems that are not yet considered well understood enough for engineering work within the IETF. Currently AI and Intent are key topics on this WG.

The **COIN proposed Research Group (COINRG)** will explore existing research and foster investigation of "Compute In the Network" and resultant impacts to the data plane. The goal is to investigate how to harness and to benefit from this emerging disruption to the Internet architecture to improve network and application performance as well as user experience. COIN will encourage scrutiny of research solutions that comprehend the re-imagining of the network to be a place where routing, compute, and storage blend.

COIN will address both controlled environments such as DCN and the ongoing shift from data center (DC) toward edge computing and will debate whether this shift can be viewed as a cloud continuum. COIN specifically will focus on the evolution necessary for networking to move beyond packet interception as the basis of network computation.

Orchestration of end-to-end resources between the DC network and the edge is another key topic to address in COIN. In particular, the RG will examine orchestration with increasingly heterogeneous distributed components and draw inspiration from current approaches (e.g., Kubernetes, Swarm) that are likely to need updating, extending, and/or simplifying in multi-domain network environments.

The IETF SFC WG, NMRG and COINRG focus on researching of new orchestration approaches, service function chaining, and enhancements to service provisioning as well as new technologies for the management of networks, exploring AI and Intent based techniques. These topics are in line with the design goal of DAEMON. Several project partners (e.g., TID, NEC, WINGS) are active in IETF and attend the regular IETF meetings. Thus, DAEMON can monitor the activities of these WGs and explore opportunities for making contributions to IETF RFCs based on the DAEMON innovations.

4.3.2.3 ETSI

ETSI is the European Telecommunication Institute, a recognized European Standards Organization dealing with telecommunications, broadcasting and other electronic communication networks and services. Most of the standardization work at ETSI is carried out in committees. Different tasks require different types of committees. Main types are:

- a) Technical Committee (TC) – addressing a number of standardization activities in a specific technology area.
- b) ETSI Project (EP) – similar to a Technical Committee but established for a fixed period of time.
- c) ETSI Partnership Project – established when there is a need to co-operate with other organizations to achieve a standardization goal. 3GPP is one of them.
- d) Industry Specification Group (ISG) – operating alongside the traditional standards-making mechanisms and focusing on a very specific activity.

The committees typically meet between two and six times a year, either on ETSI premises or on other locations. ETSI members will decide what work to be done by each committee, establishing and maintaining a work program which is made up of individual items of work.

For DAEMON project, there are opportunities to demonstrate and validate proposed standards, and to contribute project results to them. Four ETSI ISGs (all focused on *network transformation*) are directly related to DAEMON:

- a) **NFV**, on network function virtualization. The ISG on NFV at ETSI has been a leading actor in standardization of the NFV technology since 2012. Currently, the ISG aims at standardizing the interfaces for wider and richer data analytics from and to the NFV infrastructure. *DAEMON plans to impact this standardization group based on the outcome of its investigations on the NI architecture, which will involve the definition of requirements on NI interfaces and feedback on their implementation, e.g., into the OSM software.*
- b) **MEC**, on multi-access edge computing. The fast network intelligence targeted by DAEMON will need to also run at the edge of the network. Therefore, this will be the most relevant SDO where *DAEMON will push advances in the field of edge and fog orchestration via NI models at different timescales.*
- c) **ENI**, on AI-enabled network management. The Cognitive Network Management system based on AI proposed by the ETSI Industry Specification Group on 'Experiential Network Intelligence' (ISG ENI) allows operators to improve the flexibility in the network operation, by automating network configuration and monitoring processes. The overall objective is to reduce the expenditure and improve the use and maintenance of the network. *DAEMON will contribute to ETSI ENI along different axes. First, the NI architecture proposed by DAEMON will complement current proposals by the ISG with an approach based on the concertation of NI operations at different timescales. Second, the novel NI-assisted functionalities proposed by the project will allow for the automated scaling the infrastructure needed to support onboarded services. Finally, DAEMON may contribute to the ongoing Proof-of-Concept (PoC) programme held by the ISG (e.g., by promoting one of the planned PoC activity).*
- d) **ZSM**, on network service automation. ZSM is working on the definition of a network architecture that supports different functionality such as the End-to-End Network Service Management, Network Slice as a Service, Testing and Tracing. *Here DAEMON will promote the developed NI models based on self-learning techniques to ISG ZSM, as NI models are explicitly targeted by the objectives of this ISG.*

Contributions to the individual groups are prepared as documents, including the requested changes to the current version of the draft work-item results. The contributions are discussed in online or F2F meetings and the contributions comply with ETSI IPR rules.

Each ISG is appointed for a limited period, requiring explicit renewal:

- a) NFV is in its fourth two-year cycle

- a. Starting its Release 4 (cloud nativeness), after releases 1 (feasibility), 2 (interoperability), and 3 (operationalization).
- b. An additional cycle is expected.
- b) MEC is in its third two-year cycle
 - a. Essential concepts an architecture consolidated. Evolution towards cloud nativeness.
 - b. Not clear if a further cycle will be required.
- c) ENI is in its second two-year cycle
 - a. Essential concepts and architecture produced. Now focused on data and action interoperability.
 - b. A further cycle is feasible.
- d) The second ZSM two-year cycle just approved
 - a. Essential concepts and architecture being finished. Convergence with the other ISGs above.
 - b. A further cycle is almost assured.

DAEMON partners have a solid history of contributions to the relevant ETSI ISGs. For instance, UC3M had authored a use case definition and is member of two PoC, one of them in which also WINGS is one of the supporting partners. Thus, DAEMON has a high chance of impacting this SDO, either via additional use cases stemming from the architectural work or even architectural enhancements. Also, we will explore the possibilities of proposing new PoC based on the DAEMON testbeds.

4.3.2.4 ITU-T

ITU is the ONU specialized agency for ICT. The Study Groups (SG) of ITU's Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T) assemble experts from around the world to develop international standards known as Recommendations.

ITU-T is especially influential in the standardization of the transport network architecture and the specification of the underlying network nodes, systems and technologies. Thus, it is relevant to all DAEMON use cases needing eMBB and URLLC, to update the standard when the current technology cannot deal with the required performance. Contributions can be submitted only by ITU-T members. They are discussed in periodic meetings (approx. every 3-6 months), and their approval is consensus-based. In the following several focus groups related to DAEMON are listed.

The Focus Group "Autonomous Networks" (**FG AN**) was established in December 2020. Focus is on autonomous networks that possess the ability to monitor, operate, recover, heal, protect, optimize, and reconfigure themselves. The impact of autonomy on the network will be in all areas including planning, security, audit, inventory, optimization, orchestration, and quality of experience, as well as accountability for non-human decision that affect customers.

The Focus Group on Machine Learning for Future Networks (ITU FG ML5G) focuses on interfaces, network architectures, protocols, algorithms and data formats that are propaedeutic for the introduction of machine learning techniques in mobile networks. This focus group is hence a very valuable outlet for the technical solutions studied by DAEMON, across the whole spectrum of NI-assisted B5G functionalities targeted by the project.

In addition, Focus Group Technologies for Network 2030 (FG NET-2030) and G.ctn5g are within Study Groups 13 and 15, respectively. **SG13**: Future networks, with focus on IMT-2020, cloud computing and trusted network infrastructure

Functional requirements and architectures for networks supporting content delivery in IPTV, identity management, sensor networks/RFIDs, and open services and platforms for service integration and delivery. Continuing work focuses on cloud computing, ubiquitous networking, distributed service networking, ad-hoc networks, network virtualization, software-defined networking, the Internet of Things, and energy saving networks – all underscoring future networks, mobile and NGN.

Focus Group "Technologies for Network 2030" (**FG NET-2030**) was established SG13 in July 2018. Focus is on networks performing extremely fast response in critical situations and high-precision communication demands of emerging market verticals.

SG15: Networks, Technologies and Infrastructures for Transport, Access and Home

Standards for the optical transport network, access network, home network and power utility network infrastructures, systems, equipment, optical fibers and cables and the related installation, maintenance, management, test, instrumentation and measurement techniques, and control plane technologies to enable the evolution toward intelligent transport networks, including the support of smart-grid applications. Special consideration is being given to the changing telecommunication environment towards packet networks as part of the evolving next-generation (NGN) and future (FN) networks, Characteristics of transport networks to support IMT-2020/5G.

ITU-T G.ctn5G: including networks supporting the evolving needs of mobile communications (IMT-2020).

ITU-T works over study periods which last four years. The current study period is 2017-2020. The full work programs of SG13 and SG15 for the current study period can be found at the following links:

https://www.itu.int/itu-t/workprog/wp_search.aspx?sg=13.

https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/workprog/wp_search.aspx?sg=15.

The ITU-T recently launched the Focus Group on Autonomous Networks (FG-AN) which aims at fostering the research on intelligent algorithms for network automation. UC3M already contributed to this Focus Group, and together with other DAEMON partners (e.g., IMDEA) participated in the first kick-off meeting in January 2021. DAEMON will continuously monitor this FG and deliver talks to promote the discussion among relevant stakeholders.

4.3.2.5 O-RAN

The O-RAN Alliance was founded by mobile operators to evolve the radio access network. Future RANs will be built on a foundation of virtualized network elements, white-box hardware and standardized interfaces that fully embrace O-RAN's core principles of intelligence and openness. The O-RAN Alliance defines future RAN requirements and helps building a supply chain eco-system following two principles: (i) Openness – the specification of open interfaces is essential to build agile and cost-effective next-generation RANs, such that smaller vendors and operators can quickly introduce new services; and (ii) Intelligence – the advent of 5G and beyond result in highly complex networks, with high densification and richer and more demanding applications. To tame such complexity, networks in the O-RAN vision must be self-driving, leveraging new learning-based technologies to automate operational network functions and reduce operational costs. *DAEMON is perfectly aligned with the O-RAN vision, and very well positioned to influence the design of interfaces to accommodate the NI needed for the operation of virtualized RANs, including the coordination between radio and computing resources and the coordination between real and non-real-time data collection, model training and NI execution.*

The relevant working groups of ORAN for DAEMON project:

- 1) WG1: Use Cases and Overall Architecture Workgroup
- 2) WG2: The Non-real-time RAN Intelligent Controller and A1 Interface Workgroup
- 3) WG3: Near-Real-time RIC and E2 Interface Workgroup
- 4) WG6: Cloudification and Orchestration Workgroup.

Contributions to ORAN are made by O-RAN Alliance members (both operators and vendors, NBL and NEC are two of the active members). The contributions are discussed in periodic meetings and the approval is consensus-based. There are releases in O-RAN alliance for the different specifications, interfaces and software. ORAN milestones are not scheduled and there is not O-RAN Alliance wide roadmap.

DAEMON partners have been actively following the activities in O-RAN, which is quite relevant for DAEMON. In this line, NEC and NBL are the members of O-RAN and also participating in regular meetings. Thus, DAEMON has a high chance of impacting this SDO with our innovations on defining NI related functionalities and standard interfaces for Non-RT and Near-RT RIC, aligned with the scopes of the O-RAN WGs (WG1, WG2, WG3 and WG6). Also, we will explore the possibilities of proposing new PoC based on the DAEMON testbeds.

4.3.3 DAEMON standardization timeline

To create the project standardization activity roadmap, the DAEMON project will follow the steps below:

- Identify the standardization activities that are or may be relevant to DAEMON
- Map the project technology development areas onto the standardization activities from 1) above, by accounting of the timeline towards 2023
- Align the DAEMON with 5GPPP pre-standardization activities and disseminate the activities from relevant 5GPPP projects to DAEMON.

The above two steps are presented in the following sub-sections. First subsection is classifying the standardization activities to technical innovations of DAEMON project and the second section is visualizing the timeline of main standards entities towards 2023. The third section is describing the collaboration with 5GPPP pre-standards working group.

4.3.3.1 *Classification and mapping of standardization activities*

Based on the standardization activities identified above, a classification of the standardization activities per technology development area (or topic) in the project is first attempted.

Table 9. Mapping of DAEMON innovations to SDOs.

DAEMON innovation	SDO	Rationale
RIS control	O-RAN, 3GPP RAN	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) are raising interest in both O-RAN and, especially, 3GPP as a means to increase spectrum efficiency in the RAN. DAEMON can contribute with the specification of interfaces that would enable enforcing policies on the RIS controller and exchanging information (e.g., wireless channel estimates) between gNBs and RIS controller.
Multi-timescale Edge resource management	ETSI MEC, ETSI NFV	Management of edge resources is in scope of ETSI MEC and also ETSI NFV. DAEMON may set novel requirements on these standard specifications to support novel multi-timescale NI in these environments.
In-backhaul support for service intelligence	ETSI ENI, ETSI NFV	In-backhaul NI methods, functional blocks, and interfaces designed in DAEMON may induce extensions in ETSI ENI architecture. Moreover, computing-capable network forwarding elements, such as smart switches, may embed AI-capable NFVs to process data flows while they traverse the mobile backhaul system.
Compute-aware radio scheduling	O-RAN	This NI functionality is at the forefront of O-RAN jurisdiction where joint optimization of O-Cloud and O-DU/CU resources are to be expected. Innovations at both Non-RT RIC and Near-RT RIC, in addition to A1, O1, O2 and E2 interfaces are within the scope of DAEMON.
Energy-aware VNF placement	ETSI NFV, IETF SFC	Energy-awareness VNF placement could be included into the standardization path of IETF SFC and ETSI NFV by i) consolidating orchestration algorithms that take this aspect into consideration, ii) including the energy consumption of VNFs in the VNFs catalog data and, iii) including such monitoring information from the VIM.

Self-learning MANO	ETSI NFV, ETSI ENI, IETF NMRG and IETF COINRG, ITU-T FG AN and FG ML5G	ETSI NFV captures multi administrative domain instantiations of the architecture, however the Self Learning MANO (which takes into account vertical requirements) may require an extension of the interfaces. The same concept may also apply for the ETSI ENI Architecture.
Capacity forecasting	ETSI NFV, 3GPP, O-RAN	Capacity forecasting is a concept that can be applied to several entities in the standardization landscape. ETSI NFV, 3GPP (for the analytics related to the NWDAF) or O-RAN, for the capacity related to the radio.
Automated anomaly response	3GPP, ITU-T FG AN	3GPP TS23.288 [8] defined a procedure for the “Abnormal UE behaviour” analytics which may be further refined with the DAEMON findings. The ITU-T FG-AN is also looking for new solutions, where DAEMON is working, on the autonomous networks to automatically monitor, operate, recover, heal, protect, optimize, and reconfigure themselves.
NI orchestration layer	ETSI ENI, ZSM	The coordination of different NI entities is in scope with the ETSI ENI framework and the ETSI ZSM fabric, especially for MANO related purposes.

4.3.3.2 Timeline

The following figure presents a timeline of DAEMON SDOs over the lifetime of the project.

Figure 3. Timeline of SDOs relevant to DAEMON.

4.4 Open-Source plan

Contributions to open-source platforms is a key objective, set out to maximize the impact of the project. By fostering the integration of advancements to NI made by DAEMON into the relevant open-source projects, the project can ensure a significant impact on the open-source community, and in leading platforms used in both academia and industry. Any contributions made to the relevant projects should be impactful and significant. They should aim to clearly demonstrate the advancements made to each platform as a result of innovations made by DAEMON.

The project has outlined a goal of 6 contributions to open-source projects over the course of the project, as one of the main KPIs for WP6. The following open-source platforms have been identified as those most relevant to DAEMON, while also having strong links to project partners: srsRAN (srsLTE) and Eclipse

4.4.1 Open-Source work plan for year 1

The first year of open-source work will be key to early adoption of DAEMON innovations in open-source projects. The open-source work plan for Y1 will focus on the following:

- Proper definition of a "contribution to open-source projects" in the scope of DAEMON
- Identification of the specific areas of each project that DAEMON should contribute to
- Integration of the above projects in the DAEMON framework
- Make initial contributions to open-source projects
- Active engagement with the communities of the above open-source projects
- Define future open-source work plan roadmap.

The first step in the open-source work plan for Y1 is to outline an agreed definition for contributions to open-source projects, in the context of the DAEMON project. By having a known definition, it will make it easier for the project team to work towards making impactful contributions to open-source projects based on the innovations of DAEMON. A strict definition, agreed on by all members of the consortium will also help to reinforce the aims of the project laid out in the proposal. This definition must also be realistic, so that we are fully able to meet the aims set out in the project proposal of having 6 contributions to open-source projects.

Contributions should be made to the relevant areas of each open-source project. We aim to identify the key areas of each project that apply most to DAEMON by the end of Y1. Helping to aid in making impactful contributions to each project. This will also help to identify which element(s) of each open-source project DAEMON will use. Doing this will also help to identify any modifications that must be made in order to ensure stable interoperability between the DAEMON framework and the open-source elements being leveraged.

In line with the goals set out in the project proposal we aim to make at least one contribution to each of the projects mentioned above. This will set up the following contributions over the next 2 years of the project. Once each of the open-source projects being leveraged has been integrated into the DAEMON framework, we hope to begin making these contributions. By following the work-plan up until this point it is hoped that these contributions will be impactful. The initial contributions should help champion the integration of advancements to NI made by DAEMON. Helping the project to ensure a significant impact on the open-source community, and in leading platforms used in both academia and industry.

We hope to actively engage with the communities of the above open-source project once these initial contributions have been made. As a result, we will be aiming to highlight the importance and potential impact, DAEMON could have for the open-source community. This engagement will be ongoing throughout the duration of DAEMON, so as to continue to promote the work being done between contributions to open-source projects. This may take the form of tutorial like publications, public demos or involvement in open-source oriented conferences/ conventions.

As all of this work is being done it will be important to continually assess progress being made with open-source activities. By keeping an up-to-date log of all activities, and by actively reviewing our road-map and progress on a monthly basis, it is hoped that the impact of these activities will be as meaningful as possible. It will also be important for us to plan for Y2 and Y3, which is why we plan to have a road-map for the future of open-source activities by Q3 of Y1.

Overall, the work-plan for Y1 will focus on further identification of the open-source elements needed, integration of these parts to the DAEMON framework, initial contributions to open-source projects and the promotion of DAEMONS involvement in the open-source community.

4.4.2 Relevant Open-Source activities

This section presents the open-source activities used or contributed by DAEMON project.

4.4.2.1 srsRAN

The SRS software radio suite (srsRAN) provides an open-source, flexible and robust framework for 5G network R&D, prototype development and real-world deployment. The suite provides complete UE and RAN applications and is widely used for mobile wireless R&D in both academia and industry. Recognized for its stability, performance and code quality, srsRAN has provided the foundation for a broad range of successful R&D projects, featuring as a key tool in more than 200 peer-reviewed articles [3]. On the GSMA mobile security hall of fame [4], srsRAN has been leveraged by researchers making 8 of the most recent 11 Coordinated Vulnerability Disclosures (CVDs).

Under DAEMON, SRS will provide complete 5G RAN and UE solutions which can be leveraged, modified and extended to develop and demonstrate the AI-enabled Network Intelligence envisaged by the project.

DAEMON modifications and extensions will be developed on a fork of the main srsRAN project repository. This work will be released publicly under the open-source AGPLv3 license for other researchers to assess and use, supporting reproducibility of DAEMON research outputs. Use of the AGPLv3 license also ensures full compatibility with the underlying srsRAN software. Using a repository fork in this way ensures that DAEMON-specific work can easily be rebased and updated as new srsRAN software releases become available. It further allows modifications or extensions to be contributed back into the underlying srsRAN software where appropriate using the standard contribution and peer-review mechanisms used by the project.

4.4.2.2 Eclipse

The Eclipse Foundation, more in particular the Edge Native Working Group initiative fosters openly accessible solutions for Edge and Fog computing, and has taken a major lead in this domain. It provides Open-Source edge compute platforms to solve the complex challenges in decentralized environments at the mobile network edge. ADLINK, a partner in DAEMON, is a founder and steering member of the Edge Native Working Group.

Under DAEMON, ADL will provide a release for the Eclipse Zenoh [5] project planned for Q2/2021 and will be available in the official repository. Additionally, the Eclipse fog05 [6] provides a decentralised infrastructure for provisioning and managing compute, storage, communication and I/O resources available anywhere across the network. Eclipse fog05 addresses highly heterogeneous systems even those with extremely resource-constrained nodes. ADL will continue to actively participate in the different events of Eclipse IoT and Eclipse Edge, for example the presentation of the Edge Of Things: 2020 IoT Developer Survey Results [7].

4.4.3 DAEMON open-source time line

The following figure presents a timeline of DAEMON open-source projects over its lifetime.

Figure 4. Open-source time plan.

srsRAN follows a 6-month release timeline, releasing in April and October of each year. The first 5G elements will be available in the 21.04 release, with the first FOSS 5G NSA UE. The 5G NSA gNB will follow in 21.10. With the 5G SA UE and gNB following in 2022.

ADL do not have a specific timeline release for Eclipse zenoh and fog05 projects. However, depending on the features being implemented in the scope of the project, and as well as external contributions, it is expected to have 1-2 releases per year. It should be remarked that Eclipse Zenoh and Eclipse fog05 follows an open call for roadmap definition where next steps are discussed and decided within the opensource community. For this reason, at the time of writing this deliverable, it is not possible to identify the right quarter for the next releases. Eclipse zenoh and fog05 are currently available to download from the open-source repositories. The Eclipse Foundation does not follow a set release schedule, with updates being driven by ongoing projects and occurring in a more ad hoc manner than that of srsRAN.

These releases should be added to the project GitHub repository as soon as they become available. We should plan to make two contributions per year, one per project, to ensure we meet the aims set out in the project proposal.

5 Early achievements

In this section, we highlight the accomplishments for approximately three months since the DAEMON project has officially started. They are on track with the work plans detailed in the sections above.

5.1 Communication activities

In this section we report the early achievements of the project related to the communication activities. The following sections will deal with some specific aspects of communication activities since the online project kick-off on January 18, 2021 through Microsoft Teams. The first official project press release was released on February 12 2021 online. More details can also be found on the different sections of our project website <https://h2020daemon.eu/>.

5.1.1 News and press releases

Four DAEMON press articles covering the kickoff of DAEMON have been released. Specifically:

1. DAEMON: Beyond 5G with (Network) Intelligence by M. Fiore (IMDEA):
<https://networks.imdea.org/daemon-beyond-5g-with-network-intelligence/> (English) and <https://networks.imdea.org/es/daemon-mas-alla-del-5g-con-inteligencia-de-red/>
2. DAEMON: Network Intelligence Beyond 5G by B. McAuliffe and P. Sutton (SRS):
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6770742691748745216/>
3. A project investigates how to improve 6G network intelligence technology by M. Gramaglia (UC3M):
https://www.uc3m.es/ss/Satellite/UC3MInstitucional/en/Detalle/Comunicacion_C/1371306399719/1371215537949/A_project_investigates_how_to_improve_6G_network_intelligence_technology
4. Building Beyond 5G systems with NEC technology for next-generation mobile services (NEC):
<https://www.neclab.eu/about-us/press-releases/detail/building-beyond-5g-systems-with-nec-technology-for-next-generation-mobile-services>.

In addition, the following press articles covering other aspects of DAMON are listed next

1. DAEMON Eyes Greater Network Intelligence in 6G by M. Fiore (IMDEA):
<https://www.6gworld.com/exclusives/daemon-eyes-greater-network-intelligence-in-6g-systems/>
2. Un proyecto investiga cómo mejorar la inteligencia de red de la tecnología 6G by M. Gramaglia (UC3M):
https://www.uc3m.es/ss/Satellite/UC3MInstitucional/es/Detalle/Comunicacion_C/1371306398356/1371215537949/Un_proyecto_investiga_como_mejorar_la_inteligencia_de_red_de_la_tecnologia_6G.

5.1.2 Web, social media, and project communication material

The project website has been established at the beginning of the project and it is reachable at following URL: <https://h2020daemon.eu/>. The landing page is reported in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5. DAEMON website's landing page.

Some initial statistics have been gathered for the website. They are reported in the **Figure 6**. It can be observed that, since the beginning of the project (i.e., "last 60 days" statistics) about two hundred four unique visits have been achieved, reaching a total of a thousand twenty-five views. Home, Consortium, and Events did catch the largest attention, which is expected for a brand-new project.

Page title and screen class	Views	Users	New users	Views per user
Totals	1,025 100% of total	204 100% of total	205 100% of total	5.025 Avg 0%
1 Home - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIF-Learning MOBILE Networks	276	148	134	1.865
2 Home - H2020 DAEMON: Network intelligence for aDAptive and sEIF-Learning MOBILE Networks	120	61	59	1.967
3 Consortium - H2020 DAEMON: Network intelligence for aDAptive and sEIF-Learning MOBILE Networks	61	22	2	2.773
4 Consortium - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIF-Learning MOBILE Networks	52	41	5	1.268
5 News and Events - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIF-Learning MOBILE Networks	50	27	0	1.852
6 Media - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIF-Learning MOBILE Networks	47	16	2	2.938
7 Deliverables - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIF-Learning MOBILE Networks	40	23	0	1.739
8 Objectives - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIF-Learning MOBILE Networks	37	19	0	1.947

Figure 6. Most visited page.

The second report found in **Figure 7** reflects that from the 204 unique visits, Chrome web-browser counts for most of them, but somehow the engagement of Firefox users is a 30% higher.

Browser	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user	Average engagement time	Event count
Totals	204 100% of total	205 100% of total	216 100% of total	61.19% Avg 0%	1.059 Avg 0%	1m 45s Avg 0%	2,770 100% of total
1 Chrome	140	139	147	60%	1.05	1m 57s	2,057
2 Firefox	23	24	41	68.33%	1.783	2m 27s	434
3 Safari	14	14	13	72.22%	0.929	0m 54s	99
4 Edge	9	9	8	80%	0.889	1m 00s	98
5 Internet Explorer	7	7	0	0%	0	0m 00s	21
6 Safari (in-app)	5	5	4	80%	0.8	0m 23s	29
7 Android Browser	3	3	0	0%	0	0m 00s	9
8 Samsung Internet	3	3	3	75%	1	0m 34s	20
9 (not set)	1	1	0	0%	0	0m 00s	3

Figure 7. Most used web explorers & devices used to access the website.

The last webpage statistics are found in **Figure 8**, where is important to highlight the non-European audience attracted: United States of America and Qatar, having the latter the largest retention by far (i.e., 7 minutes). We can also assume that several visits come from countries where consortium member are hosted, which correlates with local promotion.

Country	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user	Average engagement time	Event count
Totals	204 100% of total	205 100% of total	216 100% of total	61.19% Avg 0%	1.059 Avg 0%	1m 45s Avg 0%	2,770 100% of total
1 Spain	42	42	61	70.11%	1.452	2m 08s	741
2 Greece	22	22	23	57.5%	1.045	1m 12s	212
3 United States	22	22	5	22.73%	0.227	0m 16s	105
4 Germany	17	16	11	50%	0.647	0m 49s	108
5 France	14	14	10	52.63%	0.714	1m 58s	123
6 Belgium	11	10	10	66.67%	0.909	0m 39s	88
7 Netherlands	11	11	15	71.43%	1.364	2m 47s	172
8 Finland	8	8	3	37.5%	0.375	0m 10s	32
9 Italy	8	7	8	88.89%	1	0m 52s	60
10 Qatar	8	8	18	62.07%	2.25	7m 16s	232

Figure 8. Geographical distribution of the website accesses.

The project has been very active on social media which accounts are the following:

1. Twitter: <https://twitter.com/h2020daemon>
2. Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/h2020daemon>
3. Facebook Page: <https://www.facebook.com/h2020daemoneu/>
4. Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/h2020daemon/>
5. LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/daemon-daemon-717591202/>.

All these accounts are shared on our webpage, and Twitter and Facebook feeds are displayed in real-time throughout it. A total of 25 meaningful posts have been shared (5 per social network). In Twitter we have reached a total of 4.3K impressions, where in Figure 9 we can see that large amount is thanks to the Women and Girls in Science Day special meeting, with 1,483 impressions, and 126 engagements counting for a rate of 8.5%. As a summary, just in Twitter our links (DAEMON webpage and press release) have been clicked 39 times, and there is an overall retweet of 18 and 32 Likes.

Figure 9. DAEMON’s Twitter analytics.

Figure 10 is the Twitter profile of DAEMON, which shows that 31 people is subscribed to our news.

Figure 10. DAEMON’s Twitter account profile.

The rest of the social networks show likewise analytics. An example is LinkedIn in **Figure 11**, with 17 profile visits, and 54 time the posts were read. Obviously, there is a correlation between how large is the number of users of a specific social network, and our analytics – for the lower audience of LinkedIn, our numbers are considerable for a brand-new research project.

Figure 11. DAEMON's LinkedIn account analytics.

We can notice the same in our Facebook page (**Figure 12**).

Published	Post	Type	Targeting	Reach	Engagement
12/02/2021 23:03	@h2020daemon sets forth an innovative and disruptive approach to			2	1 0
11/02/2021 11:17	The EU funded H2020 project DAEMON supports the International			3	1 3
19/01/2021 17:15	The second kick-off session of the EU funded H2020 project DAEMON took			8	3 2
19/01/2021 00:07	The first online session of the kick-off meeting of the EU funded H2020			7	1 1
19/01/2021 00:06	A new project has started! Since 1st January 2021 the EU funded H2020			7	0 1

Figure 12. DAEMON's Facebook account analytics.

And lastly in DAEMON's Instagram (**Figure 13**).

Figure 13. DAEMON's Instagram account profile.

In addition, the DAEMON Project Tri-Fold Kick-off Brochure was submitted and distributed as Open Access on 10th March 2021. It also contains analytics, for the number of digital views, downloads, and QR scans. While **Figure 14** shows its A-side, it is completely accessible, and ready to cite, using the following DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4593899>.

Figure 14. The H2020 European Project DAEMON Tri-Fold Kick-off Brochure.

5.1.3 Communication talks and other actions

Our communication talks (Table 11) have been given since the project started as part of the Raise Awareness Phase of the CoDEP. In this sense, the scope of the talks is general, and the focus is one explaining the high-level goals, main building blocks, and verticals involved, including the general technological framework of the project to general public.

Table 10. Communication talks.

#	Title	Event
2	5G-PPP Webinar: Europe accelerates towards 6G	Webinar: https://5g-ppp.eu/event/5g-ppp-webinar-europe-accelerates-towards-6g/

5.2 Dissemination activities

In this section, we report the dissemination activities of the project. DAEMON has carried out multiple dissemination activities, even if the project is still at its early stage, this included presentations in multiple conferences, seminars and forums.

5.2.1 Publications and technical dissemination

The following table presents DAEMON peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals and studies, demos, and posters in scientific conferences.

Table 11. Publications in scientific conferences and workshops.

Date	Title	Conference	Authors
2021/02/01	CloudLSTM: A Recurrent Neural Model for Spatiotemporal Point-cloud Stream Forecasting	The Thirty-Fifth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (AAAI-21)	M. Fiore (IMDEA)
2021/05/01	Demonstrating a Bayesian Online Learning for Energy-	The 40th Annual IEEE Conference on Computer	G. Iosifidis, A. G. Saavedra (TU Delft, NEC)

	Aware Resource Orchestration in vRANs	Communications (INFOCOM'21)	
2021/05/01	Energy-Efficient Orchestration of Metro-Scale 5G Radio Access Networks	The 40th Annual IEEE Conference on Computer Communications (INFOCOM'21)	M. Fiore (IMDEA)
2021/05/01	Bayesian Online Learning for Energy-Aware Orchestration in vRANs	The 40th Annual IEEE Conference on Computer Communications (INFOCOM'21)	G. Iosifidis, A. G. Saavedra (TU Delft, NEC)
2021/05/01	AutoML for Video Analytics with Edge Computing	The 40th Annual IEEE Conference on Computer Communications (INFOCOM'21)	G. Iosifidis (TU Delft)
2021/06/17	When Deep Learning May Not Be The Right Tool For Traffic Classification	The Sixth IEEE/IFIP International Workshop on Analytics for Network and Service Management (AnNet 2021)	M. Camelo (IMEC)
2021/06/14	No-Regret Slice Reservation Algorithms	IEEE International Conference on Communications 2021 (ICC'21)	G. Iosifidis (TU Delft)
2021/06/14	Experimental Evaluation of Power Consumption in Virtualized Base Stations	IEEE International Conference on Communications 2021 (ICC'21)	A. G. Saavedra, G. Iosifidis, (NEC, TU Delft)
2021/06/28	Category Theory Framework for Variability Models with Non-Functional Requirements	23 rd International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering (CAiSE'21)	Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Dilian Gurov, Monica Pinto, Lidia Fuentes (UMA)

Table 12. Publications in scientific journals.

#	Title	Journal	Authors
1	ProDSPL: Proactive self-adaptation based on Dynamic Software Product Lines	Journal of Systems and Software	I. Ayala, A.V. Papadopoulos, M. Amorand L. Fuentes (UMA)
2	Elastic Femtocaching: Scale, Cache and Route	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications	G. Iosifidis (TU Delft)
3	Energy-efficient Deployment of IoT Applications in Edge-based Infrastructures: A Software Product Line Approach	IEEE Internet of Things Journal	A. Cañete, M. Amor and L. Fuentes (UMA)
4	vrAln: Deep Learning based Orchestration for Computing and Radio Resources in vRAN	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing	A. Garcia-Saavedra, M. Gramaglia, A. Banchs (NEC)

5.2.2 Synergies with other projects

DAEMON has submitted a proposal, jointly with RISE6G, to organize a workshop collocated with EUCNC 2021 on the topic of Reconfigurable Intelligent surfaces.

5.3 Exploitation activities

According to the exploitation plan of DAEMON described in Section 4, each partner category, ('vendors and service providers', 'network operators', 'small and medium enterprises', and 'academia and research centers') started their activities towards their short-term exploitation objective. More evident results will be reached at the end of the first year.

Network operators: the definition of relevant use-cases for different operators and network platform. Start of prototype design and definition of requirements for the NI module to best fit the needs of each stakeholder.

SMEs: the analysis of potential contributions to open-source projects and training courses on SDN, NFV, and MEC architectures and cloud platforms has started.

Universities and R&D centers: definition and analysis of scope of their work (on topics such as multi-domain orchestration and slicing) in a 5G context towards potential exploitation has started.

5.3.1 Standardization

In addition to the creation of an initial standardization roadmap, DAEMON partners will undertake activities to disseminate the project concept and initial results at various standardization forums and other relevant standard-related forums. In this respect, the DAEMON project has joined the 5G PPP pre-standardization working group where a representative from DAEMON will participate in calls, meetings and will provide input to the deliverables.

DAEMON project has appointed a Standardization Manager (SM) to centralize and coordinate all the effort that has the potential of contributing to relevant SDOs. By doing this, we expect to maximize our contributions to standard organizations.

5.3.2 Open-Source activities

Up to this point there have been no contributions to FOSS projects. We have identified the relevant projects and have liaised with consortium members involved in the relevant projects to help align our open-source plan with srsRAN fog05 and Zenoh. It is hoped we will begin integration of these projects to the DAEMON framework in the coming months and have made our first commitments by the end of Q4 2021.

5.3.3 Bachelor, Master, PhD Theses/Courses and Internships

Table 13. DAEMON-related bachelor, master and PhD theses, and internships.

Type (PhD/Master/Bachelor/Intern)	Status (Ongoing/Finished)	Title
1. Master Thesis	Ongoing	Online Learning for Edge Network Caching (TU Delft)
2. PhD Thesis	Ongoing	Optimization Algorithms for Robust Network Intelligence (TU Delft)
3. PhD Thesis	Ongoing	Energy-efficient tasks assignment for heterogeneous deployment architectures on Edge Computing (UMA)
4. PhD Thesis	Ongoing	Achieving Energy Efficiency with a Software Product Line Engineering Approach (UMA)
5. MSc Course	Ongoing	5G Standards (UC3M)
6. MSc Course	Ongoing	B5G Operation Requirements (TU Delft)

6 References

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- [2] IPR Helpdesk. "IPR glossary". Available at: <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/glossary>
- [3] <https://www.srslte.com/research>
- [4] <https://www.gsma.com/security/gsma-mobile-security-hall-of-fame>
- [5] <https://download.eclipse.org/zenoh/zenoh/>
- [6] <https://github.com/eclipse-fog05/fog05>
- [7] https://www.crowdcast.io/e/edgeofthings_mar24_21/register
- [8] 3GPP TS 23.288 Architecture enhancements for 5G System (5GS) to support network data analytics services (Release 16), V16.6.0 (2020-12).